

**RESISTANCE IN AMBIVALENCE: READING NAFISI AND
MOAVENI BEYOND THE POLITICAL RHETORIC OF IRAN
VERSUS AMERICA**

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Abstract:

The Islamophobic gaze of the West, post 9/11, has coloured the critical reception of memoirs by Iranian American women. The narration of their lived experience in the Islamic Republic of Iran post-1979 became prey to the Eurocentric tendencies of exoticizing Muslim women as victims of 'barbaric' Islam. It was also criticised for covertly consenting to the U.S. military invasion of the Middle East. The criticisms unwittingly use the Postcolonial binary framework of Iran versus America discourse. In response, this paper reads Azar Nafisi (*Reading Lolita in Tehran*) and Azadeh Moaveni (*Lipstick Jihad*) as ambivalent subjects, neither refusing nor affirming either of the opposing political rhetoric. This paper analyses both memoirs using Julia Kristeva's concept of Intertextuality and Homi K. Bhabha's concept of 'Mimicry', 'in-betweenness' and 'third spaces'. Rather than forcefully compartmentalizing Iranian women into two opposing discourses, this study is interested in how their subjectivity is formed by the process of negotiation at the site of the textual collision and cultural antagonism. By authoring the discrimination and displacement they suffered, they are reconstructing their lost selves in the memoirs and therefore deserve readers' sympathetic attention. More importantly, this paper stresses the need for a fresh set of perspectives that transcends the political binary of Iran and America.

Keyword: Iranian women, memoirs, Islamophobia, Intertextuality, Mimicry, Nafisi, Moaveni, ambivalence, Islamic Republic of Iran, 9/11 Attack, U.S. imperialism

Introduction

The publication of memoirs by Iranian American women surged in the U.S. after 9/11, coinciding with the U.S. invasions of Iraq and Afghanistan. These memoirs, often written to reclaim personal identity and voice past silences, were instead interpreted as victim narratives justifying the "War on Terror." Azar Nafisi's *Reading Lolita in Tehran* (2003) was one of the memoirs that gained popularity in the U.S. It covers Nafisi's return to Iran after the Revolution of 1979 to the year 1997. She describes living under a regime that forced women to wear veils and banned Western literature. As an English professor under constant surveillance, she eventually resigned and secretly taught forbidden Western classics to a select group of students at her home. This article focuses on another memoir written by Azadeh Moaveni titled *Lipstick Jihad: A Memoir of Growing Up Iranian in America and American in Iran* (2005). It describes Moaveni's struggle with her hyphenated identity as a second-generation Iranian American and her travel to Iran as a journalist reporting for *Time* Magazine. She narrates at length about the transgressive youth culture in contemporary Iran she witnessed.

Despite receiving great success for its literary value, Nafisi attracted several critical remarks on her usage of the Western Orientalist framework. To elaborate on this, Mitra Rastegar explains in her essay that Nafisi reframes her work using Orientalist binary tradition where she positions the West as modern, rational and dynamic as opposed to the East as static, irrational and antimodern (2006, p. 108). In addition to this, Anne Donadey and Huma Ahmed-Ghosh argue that this memoir's greatest weakness is that it was written exclusively in terms of Iranian context and it doesn't provide the historical and political tools for Western readers to understand the real situation of the events present in it (2008, p. 624). They refer to Leila Ahmed to further stress the need to emphasize context when moving from a Middle Eastern location to a Western location as it uproots colonialist and orientalist stereotypes of backward Islam and oppressed Muslim women (2008, p. 633-34). As a result of Nafisi's exclusion of historical and political context, the memoir does become susceptible to racist and Islamophobic interpretations.

Hamid Dabashi, in his book *Brown Skin White Mask*, labels memoirists like Nafisi as “Native informants”. According to him, they “feign authority, authenticity, and native knowledge (2011, p. 72). He scrutinized these intellectual expatriates for using their nativeness to share inside information catering to the interest of the West in the Middle East. Nafisi and Moaveni both belong to upper-class families who were directly affected by the revolution and could afford to go into exile. Since privileged members of the Iranian society are initiating a conversation in the West, Dabashi shows concern about the possible peril of their personal stories being deemed as representative of all Iranian women. All in all, he explains the West's tendency to appropriate their testimonies to manufacture consent for the ‘war on terror’, justifying U.S. imperialistic agendas. Colleen Lutz Clemensa exonerates Nafisi against Dabashi's accusations, highlighting that his criticism of her seems like victim-blaming (2014, p. 587). Her plight as a woman comes as an afterthought so that Dabashi can talk about the larger political issues of how Nafisi's text hurts women in Iran (2014, p. 590). Clemensa believes that in a culture that wanted to erase women's agency and drive them back to the household, they chose to redefine their allotted prison to their advantage. The book is about Nafisi's struggle for selfhood and how imagination and reading became tools of resistance for her. She further defends that the dissemination of her text is beyond her control and the reader's interpretation of the text does not make Nafisi a “Native informant” (Clemensa, 2014, p. 585).

This article acknowledges that the memoir may lend itself susceptible to Western readers’ tendency to exoticize Muslim women as victims to suit their prejudiced anti-Islamic rhetoric. However, this study believes it is much more important that we acknowledge these women in the act of redefining themselves through these memoirs. They are *writing* the silences of their past selves enforced by the totalitarian regime (emphasis added). We must witness these women in the act of liberation with empathy and sensitivity rather than politically appropriating their stories into two polarizing ideologies. Critics have excessively and unwittingly analyzed these texts using the Postcolonial binary of the West and the Other. Nafisi, disillusioned after returning to post-revolution Iran, and Moaveni, an Iranian-American grappling with dual identities, both felt alienated in their homeland. Their identities, shaped by both cultures, defy simple categorization. Previous readings criticize women like them,

already oppressed by extreme patriarchy, for allegedly fostering Islamophobia in the West. This paper, therefore, uses the concept of Intertextuality by Julia Kristeva and Homi K. Bhabha's concept of hybridity, mimicry and third spaces as it allows the creation of multiple meanings at the boundaries of two opposing ideas or cultures. This research aims to read Nafisi and Moaveni creating a space for themselves that is in negotiation with the two political discourses. Its goal is to analyze the ways they transgress and protect their individuality against extreme political control rather than unwittingly labelling them as victims. This study is important as it contributes an alternative perspective to the ongoing conversation about the rise of memoirs written by Iranian American women. One that avoids their voices disappearing at all costs between the larger political rhetoric i.e. Islam versus West. The paper begins with a brief historical background of Iran and then moves on to the main section which includes an analysis of the texts using Kristeva and Bhabha's theoretical frameworks. In the end, it responds to the accusation placed on the memoirists of creating Islamophobic stereotypes in the U.S.

Historical and Political Background

The novel idea behind the Islamic Republic of Iran was the collaboration between theocracy and democracy. The main issue was the proper role of religion in government, that is the emulation of *Sharia* in defining social norms and regulating personal and political relations (Mir-Hosseini and Tapper, 2006, p. 2). The aim was to free Iran from the despotism of its earlier ruler. Instead, Iran experienced changing hands from autocracy to theocracy, substituting one form of despotism with another (2006, p. 2). In the early 19th Century, Iran found itself the object of Imperial rivalry between Russia and Britain. Owing to the presence of European diplomats, merchants and military advisors, the country was exposed to new Western ideas (2006, p. 11). Iranian society experienced socio-political and religious shifts as it oscillated between extreme Western influences and strict religious control. Elite families began sending their children to study in Europe and America, a status symbol linked to creating a Western-educated labour pool in Iran (Donadey and Ahmed-Ghosh 2008, p. 625).

In the 1930s, Reza Shah Pahlavi initiated Iran's modernization, including banning the veil for women. After his forced abdication in 1941, his son,

Mohammad Reza, relied on the CIA to suppress political and religious dissent. The reforms, viewed as Westernized, alienated working and middle-class women who continued veiling, exacerbating tensions between secularists and clergy. By the 1970s, Ayatollah Khomeini gained support from lower-class Iranians, who felt marginalized by the Shah's policies. After the 1979 Islamic Revolution, Khomeini's policies benefited working-class women but had less impact on middle and upper-class women, who already had access to education and healthcare (Donadey and Ahmed-Ghosh 2008, p. 626). In the early months of the Republic, religious extremists enforced strict Islamic laws, mandating veils, banning women from workplaces, stripping some legal rights, and enforcing *mahram*ⁱ. Protests erupted nationwide in response.

After the 1980 Iran-Iraq war, many widowed women sought legal changes to work and inherit property. By the early 1990s, scholars began advocating for women's rights using Islamic texts, contrasting with pre-revolutionary feminism that focused on individual rights like clothing and education, based on Western secular frameworks (Donadey and Ahmed-Ghosh 2008, p. 624-25). This led to the rise of Iranian Islamist feminists advocating for their own Qur'anic interpretations rather than relying on male clergy. They used magazines like *Zanan* and *Kiyan* to challenge clerical interpretations and integrate Western feminist perspectives. Influenced by Dr. Abdul Karim Soroush, they argue for separating state and religion on women's rights and propose a flexible interpretation of Sharia that adapts to contemporary realities, rejecting the notion of absolute Islamic truth which, in his view, turns religion into ideology (Ahmadi 2006, p. 40). This line of thinking came to be known as the New Religious thinking. To sum up, there are polarized opinions on women's rights in Iran, dipping toes between a secular and Islamic understanding of feminism.

Reading Lolita in Tehran as an Intertextual work

The term 'Intertextuality' was coined by Julia Kristeva in the 1960s influenced by Mikail Bakhtin's concept of "Dialogism" and "Ambivalence". The theory suggests that "any text is constructed as a mosaic of quotations; any text is the absorption and transformation of

ⁱ Male-female segregation and permission of the eldest male in the house before a woman could travel.

another” (Kristeva 1986, p. 37). This implies that a *text* is a composition of multiple other *texts* in negotiation with each other creating a coherent meaning as a result. Norman Fairclough operationalizes the concept of Intertextuality to enable critical analysis of texts. This theory works under the assumption that a writer is first the reader of past texts. The past texts, as a result, often subsume themselves in the process of writing. This entails that the author of the main text is also the interpreter of the texts it incorporates, responds, absorbs, transforms, interrogates or negotiates with. Fairclough further explains that the theory cannot exist in isolation and needs to be combined with power relations and how they shape social structures that determine hegemonic control (1992, p. 271). The author/interpreter is a social subject with social experiences and resources variously oriented to the multiple dimensions of social life (1992, p. 292). This denotes that the author’s subjectivity would determine how the intertextual chains would form ‘coherent’ connections to each other in a way that all texts develop ‘relational meanings’.

As per Fairclough’s conceptualisation of what he calls Manifest intertextuality, individual other texts are explicitly present in the text under analysis and are determined by the usage of quotation marks. The nature of such quotations or references in the main text is not a mere invocation or imitation as it is removed from its original position and is crafted to create multiple meanings. Whereas in interdiscursivity, the intertextuality of a text is the configuration of discourse conventions (genres, discourse, styles, activity, types) that goes into its production (Fairclough 1992, p. 271). It means that the conventions of the prior text are mirrored in the production of the conventions of the new texts. The embodiment of multiple references or conventions allows the creation of multiple meanings that refute any singular understanding of the intertext.

Since the meaning and intention of the text are not fixed or absolute, the application of this theory to Nafisi’s memoir would disprove her use of an Oriental framework that depicts the West as modern and rational as opposed to the irrational and backward East. Nafisi recounts her time studying in England and the U.S., using Western literary styles to reinterpret canonical works by Nabokov, Fitzgerald, James, and Austen. She adapts these works to reflect her own experiences in Iran, blending fiction with her reality. The reality she cannot narrate without writing about the work of fiction that she consumes during her time in Iran. The

reality she cannot narrate without writing about the work of fiction that she consumes during her time in Iran. As she proclaims in the very beginning of her memoir, “This is the story of Lolita in Tehran, how Lolita gave a different color to Tehran and how Tehran helped redefine Nabokov’s novel...” (Nafisi 2003, p. 6). Each western work she used is marked with difference yet she transformed it into producing relational meaning. The very title of the memoir suggests its intertextual nature. *Lolita* symbolizes the West, Tehran represents the theocratic regime and reading provides the bridge between these two worlds (Donadey and Ahmed-Ghosh 2008, p. 632).

After resigning from the university, Nafisi invited seven students to discuss banned fiction in secret classes. Her memoir, divided into four parts, reflects on these sessions and her life. The first and last sections, “Lolita” and “Austen,” cover the private classes from 1995 to 1997, highlighting state control over their lives. The second section, “Gatsby,” details her early years back in Iran and the ideological conflicts during her university teaching. The third section, “James,” recounts her escape into Henry James’ novels during the Iran-Iraq War (1980-88).

Nafisi begins her class by discussing a famous Persian work called *A Thousand and One Nights* (also called *Arabian Nights*). The theme of the class was the relationship between fiction and reality. Nafisi along with her students draws a parallel between herself and the storyteller Scheherazade. Besides the nature of the narrator, the memoir also mirrors the structure of *A Thousand and One Nights*. The plot centres on a king who, after discovering his queen's infidelity, kills her and her lover. To avoid further betrayal, he marries virgins and executes them the next day. Scheherazade, his new wife, uses her storytelling skills to delay her death, telling incomplete tales each night to pique his curiosity. Each story is interconnected, forming a narrative that weaves together the king’s story with Scheherazade’s tales. What Nafisi extracted from this work of fiction was how Scheherazade used her imagination to escape her death. She comments, “Scheherazade breaks the cycle of violence by choosing to embrace different terms of engagement. She fashions her universe not through physical force, as does the king, but through imagination and reflection. This gives her the courage to risk her life and sets her apart from the other characters in the tale” (Nafisi 2003, p. 19). Similarly, Imagination and reflection are also how Nafisi chose to save herself from the psychological death where she is guarding her

mind and her essence against being invaded by the state. She mirrors the persona of Scheherazade narrating her story by narrating other stories inside of it. The composition of her memoir where there are texts inside the text mimics this structural framework of stories inside of stories. This intertextual chain of texts between *Reading Lolita* and *A Thousand and One Night* is a good example of Fairclough's idea of constitutive intertextuality. The discussion on this classic fictional work foreshadows the writing of her memoir where she describes her inability to tell her story without talking about the works of imagination she read.

The next novel Nafisi discussed with her students was *Lolita* by Vladimir Nabokovⁱⁱ. The book is narrated from the perspective of an English Professor named Humbert, a paedophile who raped a twelve-year-old girl named Dolores whom he calls Lolita. The novel gained traction because of Humbert's solipsistic narration which seductively engages the reader into empathizing with him. The reader gets to see Lolita coming into existence only through his words. Nafisi alludes to Lolita's muteness in Humbert's narrative:

Humbert had tried to turn her into his fantasy, into his dead love, and he had destroyed her. The desperate truth of *Lolita*'s story is not the rape of a twelve-year-old by a dirty old man but *the confiscation of one individual's life by another*. We don't know what Lolita would have become if Humbert had not engulfed her. (Nafisi 2003, p. 33)

Similar to *Lolita*, Nafisi feels trapped by Ayatollah Khomeini's definition of an ideal Muslim woman. She feels herself becoming a "figment of someone else's dreams" where her sense of individuality, like *Lolita*, is disappearing each day (2003, p. 28). Nafisi feels invisible in her homeland as a result of someone else's fantasy of recreating women in the image of the illusory past.

Nafisi compares Humbert and Khomeini as solipsists who sacrifice others' autonomy for their own desires. Humbert controls every aspect of *Lolita*'s life, reducing her to an object of his obsession while erasing her

ⁱⁱ *Lolita* was the last work Nafisi discussed in her private class. However, she begins her memoir with it because she shares a connection to Nabokov as a writer. They have both experienced the violence of the war and lived amidst the atrocities of a totalitarian regime. Both Nafisi and Nabokov went into exile in the U.S.

true self. Nafisi uses Lolita's silence to critique the repressive nature of totalitarianism, which stifles individual happiness. She parallels this with Khomeini's regime, which, by failing to fulfil its promises, turned personal stories and bodies into tools for ideological control. Nafisi uses the metaphor of a butterfly to analyze the women in Iran and Lolita as “a living breathing human being, to become stationary, to give up her life for the still life he offers her in return” (2003, p. 37). She criticizes Humbert for his gymnastic writing style and seductive narrative technique to lure the readers away from Lolita's story into sympathizing with him. According to her, this is the second crime he committed against Lolita by never giving her a chance to articulate her story. She is commenting on Lolita's silence at the same time she is explicitly daring to write her memoir: “We told ourselves we were in that class to prevent ourselves from falling victim to this second crime” (41). She repossessed the right to narrate her own story. Here, she does not merely mirror Lolita but takes her autonomy back by overturning her victimhood. Nafisi becomes the Lolita who has to tell her story the way she wants. By reading to nourish her realm of imagination, she points out the failure of a totalitarian regime as it is unable to touch their resisting minds similar to Humbert's inability to control Lolita's inner reality. She proclaims, “No matter how repressive the state became, no matter how intimidated and frightened we were, like Lolita we tried to escape and to create our own little pockets of freedom. And like Lolita, we took every opportunity to flaunt our insubordination” (2003, p. 25-26).

In the second section, "Gatsby," Nafisi recounts her early years teaching 20th-century American literature at the University of Tehran, following Khomeini's rise to power. Teaching F. Scott Fitzgerald's *The Great Gatsby* was controversial due to growing anti-American sentiments and the novel's critique of materialism and adultery. This period saw revolutionary committees of extremist students enforcing Islamic codes on campus. They did not hesitate to criticize a professor on their dress code or to get them fired for exuberating any decadent or secular sensibilities. Nafisi was informed of a complaint against her choice of the novel by Mr Bahriⁱⁱⁱ. She decided to put the discussion of the novel in

ⁱⁱⁱ A student in Nafisi's class who is also a prominent member of the revolutionary committee on the campus. He overlooked classroom discussions and monitored teaching methods.

the form of a classroom trial. The prosecutor became her student Mr Nyazi and the defendant became a leftist student named Zarin. They battled over the relevance of this novel in the Islamic Republic of Iran.

In light of the intertextual relation, the memoir shares with this text, there exists ambivalence regarding the meaning it creates in the memoir. The interpretation of *Gatsby* from the perspective of extremist ideology takes a different tone than that of its literary merits. As the trial begins, Mr Nyazi's interpretation of the novel turns out to be politically charged with anti-American attitudes that push the thematic concerns of the work to the periphery altogether. According to Nafisi, his case against *Gatsby* became the mouthpiece of the Islamic State. He claims that the *Qur'an* is the only literature worth reading as it preaches to live a moral and just life as compared to the materialist pursuit of money that has "corrupted the western writers and deprived their work of spirituality and purpose" (Nafisi 2003, p. 125). He calls Gatsby:

A charlatan, he is an adulterer, he is a liar...this is the man Nick celebrates and feels sorry for, this man, this destroyer of homes!...the only sympathetic person here is the cuckolded husband, Mr. Wilson. When he kills Gatsby, it is the hand of God. he is the only victim. He is the genuine symbol of the oppressed, in the land of, of, of the Great Satan! (2003, p. 126-27)

Mr. Nyazi criticizes the novel for its perceived immorality, dishonesty, infidelity, and corruption, ignoring the social and economic context of the characters' lives. Nafisi uses Nyazi's argument to highlight the Iranian republic's extreme anti-American stance. She notes that Nyazi's lack of empathy for the character reflects the broader lack of empathy in the Iranian state, a recurring theme in this section of the memoir.

Zarin counters Nyazi's orthodox view by arguing that the novel critiques the association of money with happiness rather than promoting materialism. She argues, "Those who see the world in black and white, are drunk on the righteousness of their own fiction" (Nafisi 2003, 132). This critique reflects the regime's anti-American stance, where patriotism is tied to opposing American ideology, and deviation from Khomeini's vision leads to ostracism and punishment. Regulations of this nature will not do for people like Nafisi whose intellectual faculties have been shaped by Western education. Nafisi's reporting of this classroom debate in the memoir is a deliberate attempt at demonstrating

the displacement she is experiencing between these two polarising ideologies. She denotes that the state's blindness and its superficial dreams parallel the superficiality of Gatsby's dream of attracting Daisy by flaunting his financial success. His romantic delusions only resulted in his tragic death. The fixed formula of an Iranian dream is as fatal as the American dream:

How similar our own fate was becoming to Gatsby's. He wanted to fulfil his dream by repeating the past, and in the end, he discovered that the past was dead, the present a sham, and there was no future. Was this not similar to our revolution, which had come in the name of our collective past and wrecked our lives in the name of a dream? (Nafisi 2003, p. 144)

In this passage, Nafisi is critical of the republic's attempt to govern the country by incorporating the *sharia* law in the constitution without tailoring it to the present context. Without considering the changes taking place in the ever-evolving world, the republic is creating a "stagnant" and "flimsy" system of governing. Nafisi carefully constructs her ambivalent position in this section of the memoir. She is not choosing Fitzgerald over Khomeini. She is searching for her truth and finding a place that she can call her own. The place she stumbles upon in her search is what she calls the Republic of Imagination. She creates this space for herself away from the political rhetoric and "in-between" the two cultural boundaries (Bhabha, 1994).

In the third section, "James," Nafisi reflects on the role of imagination during the Iran-Iraq War (1980) while teaching Henry James' *Daisy Miller* and *Washington Square* at the University of Allameh Tabatabai. She describes how her students were puzzled by the ambiguous traits of female protagonists in James' novels, and how she copes with the war by reading James' works. What appealed to her was his discontentment towards the futility of the wars and his reluctance to engage in social and political discussions.^{iv} He wrote and read during the war to escape its chaos. Nafisi, also trapped amid the violence, found solace in James' work, which mirrored her disillusionment and anguish from the conflict. She held onto his words when he suggested that "we must for dear life

^{iv} James is an American Novelist who lived during the American Civil War (1861-65) and later became the naturalised citizen of England during the World War I (1914-18).

make our own counter realities" (2003, p. 216). He propagates the significance of "independence of thoughts" that enables the artist to enjoy the "aggression of infinite modes of being" (2003, p. 216). The displacement and irrelevance she underwent in Iran led her to seek comfort in works of fiction. Fiction allowed her the space of refuge in-between the two warring cultures. Nafisi desires similar "infinite modes of being" and "independence of thoughts" for herself. She, like James, has chosen her country to dedicate her loyalty to and that is the country of imagination, which is their home as it enables them the independence of thought that they so desire.

Nafisi dedicates a great part of this section to reporting classroom discussions on defiant female characters who are known for their lack of complicity with the social structures of their time. Characters like Daisy, Catherine Sloper in *Washington Square*, Catherine Earnshaw in *Wuthering Heights* and Jane Eyre are subversive women who refuse to be dictated to. Such complicated characters baffled her students. One such student was Mr Ghomi who questioned why they were considered revolutionary. He proclaims, "Daisy Miller is obviously a bad girl; she is reactionary and decadent. We live in a revolutionary society and our revolutionary women are those who defy the decadence of Western culture by being modest. They do not make eyes at men... He blurts out that Daisy is evil and deserves to die" (Nafisi 2003, p. 195). The quote illustrates Ghomi's limited and reductive idea of rebelling against the establishment. According to him, modesty is the only way a woman can be a revolutionary. What kind of resistance would be allowed or who would be the enemy they rebel against is also dictated by the state. Their choices are violently overridden and are justified for the elimination of the 'real enemy' i.e. America, The Great Satan. This regressive trend in the socio-political sphere made Nafisi reluctant to participate in political activities or publicly dissent. She writes that in the face of outward aggression, her desire is "to preserve a sense of personal integrity" (213). She chose to resist the regime by protecting her inner reality.

In the last section of the memoir titled "Austen", Nafisi illustrates the loss of the concept of love, the institution of marriage and the changing dynamics between men and women. She narrates how her students reveal their complicated marriages and engagements while discussing the works of Jane Austen. Nafisi alludes to the silent compassion, longing for love and mute sexual tension in Austen's novels. The iconic

line from *Pride and Prejudice* was revisioned and comically tempered by the students into Iran's current political context. Her student Yassi altered the line as: "It is the truth universally acknowledged that a Muslim man. Regardless of his fortune, must be in want of a nine-year-old virgin wife" (2003, p. 257). To which Nassrin added, "Or it is a truth universally acknowledged that a Muslim man must be in want not just of one but of many wives?". Nafisi and her students reinterpret an Austen quotation to critique post-Revolution changes in marriage rights, particularly the integration of *Sharia* law. They condemn the chauvinistic interpretation that elevated men's privileges while reducing women to second-class citizens under the guise of protecting culture from Western influence. This adapted quotation helps them reflect on and criticize their position in the new Iranian society.

Works of imagination like Austen and Nabokov were deemed dangerous in a totalitarian regime. To ban such works is to "censor the color and tones of reality to suit their black-and-white world" (Nafisi 2003, p. 277). Shaping people's mindsets would help to control them, and therefore, personal pleasures like reading must be curbed. In a society that forces everything to be political, Nafisi exposes the totalitarian regime's failure to penetrate her mind during her stay in Iran. As the Magician^v suggested to overcome tyranny, the first lesson is to do your own thing and satisfy your own conscience. Nafisi created a space of imagination to nourish her mind and soul, viewing literature not as a solution to totalitarianism but as a critical tool to confront reality and uncover truth. These texts helped her survive in Iran and preserve her individuality, intertwining with her story, as her identity is shaped by their influence. In her memoir, Nafisi plays a dual role, weaving her narrative with these texts. In the interior of the memoir, she is the silent woman who is reading for an escape from her repressed setting. Whereas on the exterior, she is the writer who is liberating herself by writing her silences. She is the interpreter of texts and the ambivalent subject that is formed through the series of intertextual chains. Nafisi's stance at the core is ambivalent as she never declared her political affiliation to either political discourse. As proven above, her story comes to life at the site of

^v Nafisi's mentor, an ex-university professor. He quit teaching as a consequence of the state's interference with the syllabus. He is called 'the magician' to maintain anonymity (Nafisi 2003).

this struggle between the two cultures. She chose herself as a woman who is the product of both cultures rather than compartmentalizing her identity as an Iranian or an American.

Cultural duality and ‘Third spaces’ in Moaveni’s *Lipstick Jihad*

Azadeh Moaveni’s memoir *Lipstick Jihad: A Memoir of Growing up Iranian in America and American in Iran* (2005) covers the struggle of a second-generation Iranian American woman living in California with her exiled family. Moaveni has absorbed her parents’ memories of Iran. The lack of inadequate memories and connections of her own drove her to return to Iran as a journalist reporting for *Time Magazine*. The memoir illustrates her struggle with dual cultural identity and linguistic conflict between English and *Farsi* or Persian. She rediscovers the underground youth culture with her fresh eyes where the Iranian youth are politically charged against the state’s repressive policies. They throw parties at home, wear make-up underneath their *chadors*, drink homemade alcohol, bring their boyfriends home since walking on the streets with a strange man is illegal, watch American sitcoms and listen to popular music privately at home, they write blogs on the internet and meet people on chat rooms, etc. Moaveni reports on the true state of contemporary urban life in Iran which is not the victim of a totalitarian regime but a country that has learnt to resist the state from entering their private lives. At the end of the memoir, she came to terms with her cultural duality and embraced her hybrid identity.

Conflict with duality seems to be a running theme in the book. The first evidence is Moaveni’s diasporic struggle between two cultures, and the other is of the urban youth’s struggle between the regime’s control and the American influences. Both Moaveni and the youth conform to neither of the opposing ideologies. Instead, they create a space for themselves ‘in-between’ the two cultures that are negotiating with each other in a state of perpetual struggle. This concept of ‘in-betweenness’ by Homi K. Bhabha rejects the binary framework that separates the West and the East as the self and the other. According to him, the binary opposition creates dichotomized, compartmentalized subjects that are fixed into two idealized images. It denies the subject of any autonomy in its existence. He believed that a subject is never stable and always exists in the ‘in-betweenness’ of two boundaries. Bhabha writes, “The ‘true’ is always marked and informed by the ambivalence of the process of

mergence itself, the productivity of meanings that construct counter knowledges *in media res*, in the very act of agonism, within the terms of negotiation (rather than negation) of oppositional and antagonistic elements” (1994, 22). Here, he explains that the subject is constructed in the interstices of two cultures. The creation of meaning never happens in the fixedness of the culture but rather in the *process*. According to him, fixed identities create an idealization of themselves that alienates the subject from its *self* (emphasis added). Subjectivity, therefore, is formed in the *process* of the hybridization of two cultures. The subject, then, has an ambivalent status.

Moaveni’s life as a diasporic subject in America is marked by a duality of culture. Her parents raised her by blending Iranian traditions with the pressures of American life, leading to identity confusion. This confusion stemmed from her parents' attempt to merge cultural experiences, as they navigated the loss of their original culture and the lack of security in their homeland. The anxiety from the loss of culture and the trauma of displacement is a driving force for her exiled family to re-create a minuscule replica of an illusory Persian experience. For example, her grandfather, Agha Joon, recreated a small garden in his San Jose apartment, echoing the lavish gardens of Iran, while her father named their car plate "RAKSH," after the hero Rostam’s steed in the *Shahnameh*. This cultural reconstruction in the host country reflects Bhabha's concept of the diasporic condition, characterized by the partial presence of the past and the repetition of life from the country of origin (Bhabha, 1994, p. 139). Growing up in a family steeped in cultural nostalgia made it challenging for Moaveni to balance her heritage with assimilating into American schools and colleges. She narrates her dilemma in her memoir as follows:

There was Azadeh at school, who managed to look and sound like the other kids, baring the occasional lunchbox oddity; and there was Azadeh at home, who lived in a separate world, with its own special language and rituals. More often, though, living between two cultures just made me long for refuge in one. Maman’s [Mother] attempts to fuse both worlds, instead of compartmentalizing them, complicated everything. She didn’t want to sacrifice anything: neither her Iranian value nor her American independence. She refused to abdicate one side for

the other, not even for a time, and it made our life together harrowing and unruly. (2005, p. 19)

The passage highlights the cultural conflicts between Moaveni and her mother during her teenage years. While Maman valued the freedom of choice afforded to women in America, she resented its permissive attitudes toward sexuality, viewing American culture as corrupt and imposed on others, while criticizing the Islamic Republic for suppressing women's individuality. This duality created a source of Moaveni's identity crisis, as her mother, though unwilling to return to Iran, resisted American materialism in raising her daughter. Moaveni's quest for identity led her to seek a connection to Iran independent of her parents' nostalgic memories, allowing her to experience a contemporary Iran distinct from their romanticized past.

Moaveni elaborates at length on the transgressive urban youth culture mostly from the middle-class and upper-class families in Tehran. She witnessed these youths navigating between the boundaries of the Islamic Republic and Western influences. Most of her anonymous informants were university students. She describes them as vibrantly sexual and partying fearlessly without any hesitation of being caught by the *Basij* or *Komiteh*.^{vi} To throw some light on it, Pardis Mahdavi's (2007) study on urban young adults in Tehran explains how they are constructing and embodying what they call a 'sexual revolution', or *enqelab-e-jensi*, in response to the social and political restrictions of the state. As Iran is theoretically a democratic theocracy governed by *sharia* law, the clauses in the law are interpreted by the clerics who hold judicial power in the parliament. This encompasses the extreme regulation of social, sexual and familial behaviours of men and women which leaves a little gap between the political and the social. Mahdavi points out that the punishment for premarital sex is death by stoning; drinking and dancing call for jail accompanied by up to 70 lashes (2007, p. 447). Yet young adults do it anyway as a form of revolting against the repressive system. Since their bodies were the site of control in the Islamic Republic, they were using it and their sexuality to speak back to the regime. They refer to this behaviour as a sexual revolution. Their detachment from the violent punishments becomes shockingly known to Moaveni after the

^{vi} Morality guards that are at every checkpoint in Tehran. They monitor the citizens to follow the Islamic codes of conduct.

incident she had with her friend Nikki. She was hanging out with Nikki and her boyfriend when they were stopped by the squad car on the street. Nikki's boyfriend was punched and kicked in front of her to see if she reacted to catch them having an illegal relationship. The officer let them go after she insisted she hadn't seen him before. Moaveni noticed that instead of being disturbed by this incident they just called it a day and moved on. What she is highlighting here is that the young population has learnt to navigate their way around the morality police rather than give up on their freedom to choose their own lifestyle. The advent of the internet became a platform where young men and women openly discussed their ideas and opinions mostly about sex. Her friend Celine revealed that people were online dating using chat rooms which allowed them to be as outrageous and indecent as they wished. What Moaveni demonstrated here is the young people's obsession with sex, a subject that is strictly forbidden in Iran. She states that they are preoccupied with sex in the "manner of dieters constantly thinking about food" (2005, p. 71). The denial of sexuality only made them more curious and creative about it. They found ways to smuggle their sexual autonomy away from the state's surveillance. They created a third space that is a carefully selected amalgamation of the two cultural discourses.

Available due to the emergence of the internet and globalization, the young generation was exposed to all things Western that they emulated in their lives and considered it as resistance to the Islamic regime rather than a sheer imitation of toxic Western culture (Mahdavi 2007, p. 451-52). This type of imitation of American popular culture resonates with Bhabha's concept of mimicry. He elaborates on the subversive nature of the mimic man who copies his colonizer's language, culture, manner and ideas as not *servicing* the colonizer's agenda. According to him, this mimicry is not an exact imitation of the colonizer but is marked by a difference. The colonial subject seems similar but is not identical, "The mimicry represents an ironic compromise" between two entities (Bhabha 1994, 86). He writes, "Colonial mimicry is the desire for a reformed, recognizable Other, *as a subject of difference that is almost the same, but not quite*. Which is to say, that the discourse of mimicry is constructed around an ambivalence; in order to be effective, mimicry must continually produce its slippage, its excess, its difference" (86). The quote states that the subject is ambivalent since the mimicry is not entirely in conformity with the idealized image it attempts to imitate.

Now, the political war between Iran and America has created two opposing sides that are constantly negating each other at the cost of the basic individual rights of the people. The ambivalence locates them 'in-between' this struggle refusing to prioritize one culture over the other. Their imitation of American popular culture is not a form of worshipping a secular superior culture as opposed to their backward orthodox Islamic culture. It is a resistance to oppression from one and a mockery of another. Since everything they did in public became a matter of political control, the desire to retain some level of autonomy was strong. She observes a sort of cultural rebellion being fought indoors defying the rigid codes of behaviour. An instance of this is when Moaveni chaperoned for her cousin Kimia at her friend's birthday party. She saw teenagers entering the house in chadors and changing into mini skirts wearing makeup and slow-dancing with their boyfriends on Toni Braxton's songs. They seemed to have transformed their house into a space where they could define their individuality and exercise free will. A space that the regime has failed to control.

In a totalitarian society, exercising freedom is different than in a democratic society. Moaveni takes note of this mode of resistance amongst the urban youth where negotiating with the system is the only way of surviving in it. They refused to choose any one symbolic power structure, existing in the 'third space' that enabled multiple possibilities to emerge in the process of negotiation. The third space, as Bhabha describes, "displaces the histories that constitute it, and sets up new structures of authority, new political initiative, which are inadequately understood through received wisdom" (Rutherford 1990, p. 211). The quote suggests that the third space undercuts the power of the structures that it emerged from and enables space for transgression and autonomy. The youth in the memoir seems to be conversing between Iranian culture and Western culture in constructing a room for individual freedom of expression. They chose to exercise individuality rather than associating themselves with any idealizing discourse which would only pin their subjectivity into compartments. An instance in the memoir that illustrates this perfectly is when Khaleh Farzi takes her to a vogue-like boutique to shop for *roopoosh*.^{vii} Moaveni showcases the emergence of a new kind of femininity where the women in Tehran have re-appropriated

^{vii} A robe or a cloak that is designed to cover the body.

the *roopoosh* and fashioned it into expressing their personality. She describes them wearing "stiletto sandals and short tunics that cinched their waist" (2005, 159) defying the norm of *not showing yourself* with robes and reversing it with *showing yourself* by self-fashioning that same robe (emphasis added). The symbol of subjugation has been modified into expressing their individuality. Moaveni attended an all-women fashion show where models were displaying new trends of *roopoosh*. A western concept adapted and transformed into displaying Iranian culture is a quaint example of the "ironic compromise" that Bhabha talks about. One can see the women declaring themselves as ambivalent subjects who are in negotiation between patriarchal control and the larger political rivalry. They have modelled "the Islamic uniform into a garment of aesthetic resistance" refusing to surrender their body and individuality (Moaveni 2005, p. 159).

As the state merged the social and the political, every activity that young Iranians did every day was either in conformity to the country's ideology or in defiance of it. The extreme attempt at the idealization of Islamic culture and its imposition on people has left them wanting refuge somewhere else. The youth, especially, would sneak and smuggle ideas from American popular culture mainly because the state left them confused and alienated from their bodies. Another instance of this sneaking 'in-between' the spaces would be Moaveni's reporting of the public gathering for the celebration and mourning during the holy month of *Muharram*.^{viii} The young adults exploit this religious gathering to come out on the street to meet people for dates. Before the revolution, people celebrated this month tamely but in recent years it is celebrated like a carnival where they are supposedly mourning the death of Hossein, calling it the "Hossein Party" (Moaveni 2005, p. 57-58). Young women hid a small piece of paper carrying their numbers under the candles they carried, and after much surveying, they would pass it to a lucky mourner. This example demonstrates the depth of how alienated Iranians have become from their own culture and religion. Religiosity lost its essence in the process of imposition of an idealized concept of Islam. The loss of culture was not just felt by the Iranians in exiled

^{viii} In the 7th Century, this month was when the prophet's grandson Hossein was martyred in the holy city of Karbala, a significant date in the early schism between Sunni and Shiite Islam. (Moaveni 2005)

diasporic communities in the U.S. but also amongst the Iranians that stayed in Iran. The political tension between two nations often ends up overconsuming the discourse of national identities neglecting other aspects of identities like gender, sexuality, class or race. The extreme dichotomy between Iran and America affected the other multitudes of identity, especially when it comes to the women question. However, Moaveni does not describe Iranian people in the memoir as static in their victimhood rather they are seen constantly resisting their repressive surroundings. Moaveni and the Iranian youth, therefore, have transcended the confinements of duality and created a new liberating space for themselves that is the product of negotiation 'in-between' two oppositional cultures.

Are Nafisi and Moaveni 'native informants'?

Hamid Dabashi, in his book *Brown Skin, White Masks*, elaborates on the changes in racist power relations where brown is the new black and Muslim is the new Jew. Dabashi accuses the U.S. imperialist forces of appearing as the victim of terrorism meanwhile perpetrating justified violence on Muslim societies, making an outward appearance of saving the Muslim world from its own barbarism (2011, p. 6). He looks at the growth of memoirs written by Muslim women after the 9/11 attack with great scrutiny. The cause of its popularity is of course tainted by the political climate of the U.S. which had declared a "War on terror" on the countries in the "Axis of Evil". Arabs and Muslims have become the new demons in the aftermath of 9/11 (p. 35). According to him, this body of confessional works created legitimate concerns about the plight of Muslim women in the Islamic world and caters to the logic of American warmongering (p. 69). He appropriated G. C. Spivak's concept of 'Native Informant' to identify expatriate intellectuals like Nafisi and Moaveni^{ix} for painting a barbaric picture of Muslim societies legitimizing their fear towards Islam. This account of Muslim women suits the needs of U.S. Propaganda thereby justifying their post-9/11 imperial projects (p. 33-35). These memoirs enable them to appear as the

^{ix} Dabashi criticised several memoirists, both men and women. Nafisi, however, received the brunt of his scrutiny. He doesn't mention Moaveni in his book. This paper extends his allegations to her as it is applicable to this study.

saviour of Muslim women rather than the neo-imperialist power.^x He harshly calls them careerists who have failed to make their career in their native land and after feeling alienated from it, adopted a home in the country where they can best sell their services. Dabashi's argument meticulously elucidated the part publications of said memoirs played in manufacturing consent for the U.S. military invasion in the Middle East. However, his criticism is politically constrained and one-sided. His sole concern with the memoirs is with their reception and not their content. Overly conscious of the Islamophobic sensibility of the West, his criticism takes the shape of victim-blaming. He focused only on Nafisi as an intellectual and conveniently blinded himself to Nafisi as a woman. His apathetic gaze overlooks the fact that a professor who teaches English Literature for a living would be consumed by her love for works of fiction. At the heart of Nafisi's memoir is the plight of a woman who has suffered physical disappearance from the public sphere and psychic mutilation of her intellectual capabilities in a totalitarian regime. Western readers see her as the victim of Islamic terrorism and Dabashi labelled her as a native informant. Neither one of these parties extended the courtesy of acknowledging her as a woman reclaiming her body and writing her personal history amidst patriarchal oppression and racial discrimination. Her memoir is excessively politicized to suit their limited perspective or propaganda. Dabashi audaciously attacks the narrative technique she chose to write her story and parades it as discriminatory to the entire Muslim world. In his criticisms, he denies her a sense of individuality just like the regime denied her basic individual rights.

Accusations of fostering Islamophobia may deter Muslim women from challenging oppressive systems, fearing their words could be misused to justify war. Moaveni, in her memoir, discusses this dilemma, feeling the weight of potential political manipulation after returning to America. Often questioned by her white friends about Iranian women, she was uncomfortable defending an entire nation, recognizing that her criticisms of the Islamic Republic could be weaponized to legitimize attacks on the Muslim world. Her mother, aware of America's Islamophobic gaze, chose silence to prevent her voice from benefiting the U.S. This political

^x Here, Dabashi refers to Spivak's analysis of covert colonial manipulation where "White men are saving brown women from brown men". The famous quote is from her essay "Can the subaltern speak?" (Spivak 1988, 296)

tension hindered progress for Iranian women, both in Iran and America. Let this be emphasized that they have the right to dissent against the system that discriminates based on gender as well as the system that discriminates based on race and religion.

Accounts of women have always run the danger of disappearing from mainstream historical events. Writing a memoir allows women to interrogate their private relationship to a historical event (Buss 2002, 3). This paper therefore emphasizes the significance of a tradition of writings by Middle Eastern women. As Helen Cixous rightly prompted, "Women must write her self... from which they have been driven away as violently as from their bodies...women must put herself into the text--as into the world and into history--by her own movement" (1976, 875). The Islamic Republic's enforcement of veils removed women from public space and desexualized their bodies, turning them into sites of political control. Nafisi's traumatic experience in Iran led her to reclaim her body through her memoir, transforming past silences into history. Rather than politicizing these voices, readers should approach them with empathy, recognizing their efforts to reclaim their humanity. Denying these women the right to speak due to potential Islamophobic interpretations only perpetuates injustice. There must be a safe space for them to exist as living, breathing individuals.

The critical reception of memoirs by Iranian American women often ranges from the Eurocentric exoticization of Muslim women to allegations of reinforcing Islamophobic stereotypes. Critics overlook the ambivalence of these subjects navigating two cultures. This paper examines Nafisi's memoir as an intertext that recontextualizes Western texts within an Iranian framework, challenging claims that she perpetuates orientalist tropes. In contrast, Moaveni's memoir uses mimicry to show Iranian youth adopting American culture as resistance to the Islamic regime. Both memoirists reveal complex negotiations and resistances without aligning strictly with either nationality. This study advocates for analyzing diasporic subjects beyond simplistic political binaries, as Bhabha suggests, offering a nuanced perspective on Iranian American women's writings.

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